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Microgram Determination of Some Antipy- rines with N-bromosuccinimide.

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ANTIPYRINE and its derivatives, amidopyrine, analgin, novalgin and dolazine are important organic compounds widely used as pain relieving drugs. Several photometric methods using potassium ferricyanide¹, sodium nitrite², *p*-dimethyl amino benzaldehyde³, bromothymol blue⁴ and potassium aurichloride⁵ reagents have been reported for their determination.

We describe here the reaction of N-bromo-succinimide (NBS) with antipyrine and its derivatives in acetic acid medium. The colour of the reaction mixture has been utilized to develop a spectrophotometric method for the determination of the compounds in microgram amounts within $\pm 2\%$ error.

Experimental

Reagents : NBS solution (0.02 M) was prepared⁶ and standardised iodometrically⁶. Stock solutions of the samples were prepared by dissolving accurately weighed amounts of antipyrine, amidopyrine, analgin, novalgin, dolazine in distilled water in 100 ml volumetric flasks. Different aliquots of the solutions were used to have concentration range of 40-900 μg . The glacial acetic acid was B.D.H. A.R. quality.

Apparatus : Beckman model DU spectrophotometer equipped with a photomultiplier tube was

used for absorption measurements. Measurements at wavelength 290 nm were done using Beckman 1.005 cm silica cells.

Procedure : 5 ml aliquots from the stock solutions were taken in 25 ml volumetric flask to which 5 ml glacial acetic acid and 5 ml NBS (0.02 M) solution were added. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 15 min and made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the solution was measured against a reagent blank in the region of 250-450 nm (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Spectrum of (A) N-Bromosuccinimide, (B) Antipyrine, (C) Amidopyrine, (D) Analgin, (E) Novalgin, (F) Dolazine

Fig. 2. Spectrum of N-Bromosuccinimide and (A) Antipyrine, (B) Amidopyrine, (C) Analgin, (D) Novalgin, (E) Dolazine in acetic acid medium.

Calibration curves were prepared and it was found that the absorbtion follows a linear relationship to concentration. The amount of the drug in unknown samples was determined by measuring its absorbance at 290 nm and referring the data to the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The spectra of antipyrine, amidopyrine, analgin, novalgin, dolazine and NBS are recorded in Fig. 1. Antipyrine and its derivatives produce a stable yellow colour with NBS in acetic acid medium.

NOTES

The spectrum of the reaction product of each compound is recorded in Fig. 2.

It has been observed that absorbance increases up to 15 min of reaction time and then becomes constant. Variation in the amount of acetic acid has no effect on absorbance at 290 nm. The absorbance increases till 0.05 M of NBS and becomes constant beyond this concentration.

NBS has been used by various workers⁷⁻¹¹ as a brominating reagent in polar media through Br⁺ species. In the present investigation it is proposed that antipyrine reacts with NBS to form monobromoantipyrine, which is responsible for the yellow colour. Monobromoantipyrine was isolated as the final reaction product (m.p. 117° having 28.7% bromine) with NBS in acetic acid media. The spectra of isolated monobromoantipyrine is similar to the spectra of A in Fig. 2.

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